

THE IMPORTANCE OF LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN THE MODERN LIFE FOR XXI CENTURY SPECIALISTS

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Abstract. *The importance of language in the modern world is constantly increasing. In the process of studying this topic, I had to be acquainted with a large number of literary sources. In the sociological literature, serious attention is currently paid to the study of problems of language and language education. At the same time, different authors give their own sociological interpretation of this concept. Therefore, for example, some define language as a primary, original reality that opens up new possibilities for a person. And language activity - as a phenomenon that ensures the qualitative uniqueness of society. Others believe that language is decisive in the choice of work and life activities and affects the intensity of interethnic relations.*

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E.A. Mikhaleva in the article “Language education as a component of an individual’s economic capital in the modern labor market” [3] writes that in modern ethnocultural conditions, characterized by bi- and multilingualism in the work environment, knowledge of languages is the most important component of the intellectual capital of employees. One of the most important requirements currently imposed on everyone who has the right to make management decisions at different levels is knowledge of languages that take place in the work environment. According to studies, the importance of language education in the modern labor market is paramount. A specialist who knows any foreign language can count on access to international contacts.

The author of the article “Language for a Careerist” E. Kryukova believes that English has become a means of international communication. If you own it, it means you stand out from other applicants. True, there are now many specialists “with the language” on the labor market. To stand out against their background, you need to have a good knowledge of financial, legal or other industry terminology in English. A foreigner must be part of the applicant's gentleman's kit, even if this is not required for the job. Knowledge of another language is akin to the ability to use an Internet search engine and negotiate. This should be in the arsenal of every specialist [1].

In the article “Language Competence and Social Mobility” O.S. Kryukova examines the influence of language competence and educational level on changes in a person’s social status. The author notes that the language factor, both at the historical and modern levels, influences social mobility. The choice of language of instruction or target language carries social prestige in many societies. In modern society, this language is English; in the 18th century. German was a socially prestigious language, and in the 19th century. - French. Nowadays, obtaining a socially prestigious job requires a high level of proficiency in a foreign language (mainly English) and, as a rule, confirmed by a special certificate [2]. Over the past 10 years, colossal socio-political and socio-economic transformations have taken place in the Republic. Foreign languages are becoming really in demand, and the motivation to study them increases significantly. A student who speaks several languages has a better chance of receiving an appropriate education and work both in our

country and in the international market. Learning languages contributes to the acquisition of additional cultural wealth, personal development, professional and career growth.

In our information age, a huge amount of knowledge is found on the Internet. Television, radio, and the media are also strong information channels from which one can draw knowledge without much expense. But the problem is that 80% of the information is stored in English electronically around the world. Books written in other foreign languages are translated, first of all, into English. In the world of science, English is the main working language. Over 2/3 of scientific literature is read in English.

The modern world is changing so quickly that those who do not keep up with the demands it makes find themselves on the margins of life. Knowing a foreign language is another survival tool. Knowledge of a foreign language today is no longer an advantage or simply a valuable quality - it has become a necessity. Given equal data, a person who speaks a foreign language increases the chance of getting a good job. And even more so, this chance increases if a person speaks a language for special purposes, i.e., professionally directed.

An increasing number of graduates of educational institutions cannot find work in their specialty; many labor units periodically fall under layoffs. The employment problem cannot be solved once and for all. Employers are interested in the length of service, experience, and skills that a potential employee has.

One of the ways to increase competitiveness in the labor market can be to study or improve a foreign language.

The purpose of this article is to identify and substantiate the relationship between knowledge of a foreign language and professionalism.

In our opinion, a specialist who has professional skills and is fluent in a foreign language has a better chance of getting a decent job and successfully moving up the career ladder. At all times, the primary goal of education has been the harmonious, comprehensive development of personality, the formation of moral, moral, and ethical qualities of students with an active civic position, capable of honoring and preserving the traditions of their people and accepting and respecting the cultural and historical heritage of other peoples. And it is the teacher, the pedagogue, who is entrusted with this responsible mission - the formation of conscious, intellectually, spiritually and morally developed citizens. The special nature of educational activity is emphasized by I. A. Kolesnikova, who believes that “upbringing does not exist separately, being integrated into other types of activity and pedagogical processes and being closely connected with them, upbringing has a pronounced specificity” [1, p. 4-5]. Through education, a person is introduced to culture, acquires spiritual values, his orientation is formed and creative activity develops.

Today, education, like other areas, is undergoing informatization; high school students already have extensive knowledge in the field of Internet technologies, but most often their work and communication on networks take the form of entertainment, while cognitive, in particular educational, motives for working with a computer cost little. Isn't it in last place? Therefore, teachers must make information and communication technologies (hereinafter referred to as ICT) a tool, a means of not only teaching, but also educating older schoolchildren.

It is obvious that when choosing educational strategies in the educational process, the teacher faces certain difficulties. If we are talking about the implementation of the educational aspect in foreign language education based on the use of Internet resources, then the teacher has to not only promote the development of the student as an intellectual, spiritual and moral

personality, but also be competent in the field of ICT, through which it now seems possible to form a creative, social active personality. As O.V. Zavalishina notes, “modern education is already unthinkable without the introduction of innovative techniques into the educational process, network technologies are becoming a natural part of it, and the inability to work with ICT will soon be equated with illiteracy” [2, p. 5]. This fact makes it an essential condition for teachers to involve and actively use modern ICT in the classroom. At the same time, not only the organization and structure of a foreign language lesson changes, but also the features of the teacher’s pedagogical activity. We should not forget that the teacher faces the most important task - education.

In order to determine the content of the educational aspect, let us turn to E.I. Passov, who gives a list of educational goals and objectives of foreign language education. These are national values, life as a value, world culture, freedoms and individual rights, communication and cooperation [3, p. 267-268]. The formation of national values among students is the primary goal for the teacher. Of course, in achieving this goal, each teacher must change pedagogical practice, which now implies the inclusion and use of Internet resources and digital educational resources when organizing individual, pair and group work of students. It is important for a teacher to know where and when to use ICT to work in the classroom, to manage the educational process, not only for the development of students, but also for their personal development and growth as a professional. Teachers are also required to be able not only to use ICT to organize work, but also to evaluate it, draw up thematic plans and maintain thematic reports.

Thus, to solve life problems that may be related to nature, human life, health protection, and conflict resolution, a teacher can use social multimedia services in his teaching practice that allow him to view photographs on the required topic, video recordings of speeches of scientists, eyewitnesses of events, educational audio recordings and videos. Using materials from multimedia services, the teacher selects, develops and, together with students, conducts educational activities aimed at developing a humanistic worldview, respect for nature, and a rational attitude towards life. The teacher has to change the curriculum in such a way as to ensure a deep assimilation of knowledge that all participants in the educational process could apply in practice to solve specific problems, as well as adequately assess the abilities of schoolchildren [7]. At the same time, learning becomes personally oriented, and the use of network resources provides access to a vast amount of information. However, a prerequisite should be the processing of the information found on the topic, “passing” it through the prism of one’s own consciousness, and not blind belief in its accuracy and truth. It is imperative for a teacher to masterfully use modern technologies to develop plans, evaluate work in class and extracurricular activities online, contact experts on the chosen topic, communicate with other teachers and use the network to exchange experiences with colleagues, and as a result grow personally and professionally.

In a foreign language lesson, it is very important to give schoolchildren an idea not only about the country of the language being studied, but also about world culture as a whole. Authentic videos and audio recordings, communication on social networks and Skype with native speakers of the target language, and joint projects aimed at studying world literature, science, cultural and art monuments come to the rescue. At the same time, world culture is a value, and the joint work of the teacher and students goes beyond the usual lesson and extracurricular activities. Now the teacher has an excellent opportunity not only to carry out the process of education and training in the classroom, but also widely using virtual communication. This ensures the integration of one’s

own knowledge with new knowledge obtained through independent search and mini-research. Throughout the entire work, the teacher does not fade into the background, but actively acts as a mentor, helping all participants in the educational process master the skills that are most in demand in modern society [8].

At the same time as the students, the teacher himself has to improve, so we can say that the learning process becomes mutual. At the same time, such values as communication and cooperation are manifested, because now all participants in the communicative process are equal, cooperation between the teacher and schoolchildren promotes respect for the opinions of other people, their views, way of activity, and teaches to achieve general agreement when there are differences in views on a particular problem. At the same time, such values as freedom and individual rights, the right of everyone to have their own position and their own vision of a particular problem are also touched upon, because by showing respect for the opinions of others, accepting points of view that are radically different from their own, schoolchildren learn to respect dignity other people.

So, it is obvious that the key to successful work as a foreign language teacher in the modern information society is not only constant self-education, knowledge and mastery of various methods and forms of teaching, but also the ability to live in the information world.

Therefore, every modern teacher must understand the role of ICT in education, be able to evaluate the results of activities that go beyond the scope of a classical lesson, and be able to plan a lesson taking into account the specifics of the use of information technology. Now an important aspect is the integration of traditional teaching practices and methods of working with ICT. An integral part of a teacher's work is the organization and management of the educational process in various conditions using Internet resources, as well as the use of innovative technologies to improve their professionalism and productivity. It is very important for teachers to know and be able to comply with the requirements for safe work on the Internet.

However, we should not forget about the system of values that determine the content of the educational aspect of foreign language education, and which, according to E.I. Passov, allow us to raise a spiritual person. Therefore, the use of ICT should be more focused on the implementation of the educational aspect, because it is education that turns every student into a Person with a capital "H," a real personality with an established system of values and beliefs, a worthy representative of his country, who respects and accepts the property and characteristics of other cultures [9].

A foreign language cannot be taught, it can only be learned. Until students realize the need to speak a foreign language, their professionalism will not meet modern requirements. The real professional orientation of the content of a foreign language course, the cooperation of language teachers and teachers of special disciplines, the selection of modern methods, and the use of technical teaching aids contribute not only to the high-quality training of a specialist, but also to the formation of him as an active personality, ready for self-education, self-development, and self-improvement.

In the course of our research, we came to the following conclusions.

Knowledge of English is essential for a 21st century professional, no matter what job you choose. Knowledge of a foreign language opens up wide opportunities for a person - communication, education and a successful career.

The English language penetrates our lives, whether we want it or not. English is the language of business people, diplomacy in international relations, science, business and commerce. English is needed to obtain a sought-after profession, to improve one's social status, increase self-esteem, etc., everyone needs it! English has become an international language. English is the language of technology.

Today it is becoming necessary to use a foreign language for a career. This is the key to success in all endeavors! Today, knowledge of English is becoming a mandatory requirement not only for foreigners. Fluency in a foreign language, along with good professional skills, will allow a specialist to get a decent job and build a successful career. Knowledge of foreign languages is one of the requirements of the modern world and opens up the possibility of obtaining a new, better-paid job and better prospects in life. Knowledge of English will enrich and expand the boundaries of your life! This is one of the important building blocks on which our whole life is built.

Knowledge of a foreign language is pride, confidence, support and self-affirmation. Learn a foreign language and your world will become brighter!

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